

INVESTIGATION ON NICKEL AMMINES. PART III. INFLUENCE OF HEATING, AGEING AND DEHYDRATION OF THE NICKELOUS HYDROXIDE ON ITS SOLUBILITY IN AQUEOUS AMMONIA SOLUTIONS

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The results on the influence of precipitation on the nickelous hydroxide in the hot, ageing and dehydration, on its solubility in ammonia solution have been described and the results interpreted on the basis of the amphoteric nature of nickel hydroxide.

Wide variation and anomalies in the solubility of nickelous hydroxide, noted by various workers, as has been pointed out in an earlier communication (Part II, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 679), is evidently due to the fact that the earlier workers failed to recognise the importance of the condition of precipitation and the relationship of the solubility with the character of the precipitate.

In our detailed study of the effect of some varying conditions on the solubility of nickelous hydroxide we have already noted (*loc. cit.*) that the solubility of the nickelous hydroxide in ammonia solutions decreases with increasing amount of alkali in the cold. Further, the size of particles has no appreciable effect on the solubility.

In the present communication we have described our experimental results of the quantitative study of the effect on the solubility of the hydroxide due to the following factors:—

1. Precipitation of the hydroxide with varying amounts of alkali in the hot.
2. Ageing of the precipitated hydroxide.
3. Dehydration of the hydroxide at various temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Effect of Precipitation of the Hydroxide with Varying Amounts of Alkali in the hot on its Solubility

M/2-Nickel sulphate solutions (150 c.c.) were taken in three separate vessels A, B and C. In each 1.082 N caustic soda solution amounting to 20 c.c. less than the equivalent, equivalent, and 20 c.c. more than the equivalent amount respectively were added in the hot (temperature 80°-90°) with constant agitation.

The precipitates with their mother-liquor were boiled for some time and filtered. The precipitates were washed completely free of nickel, where present, hydroxyl ions and majority of sulphate ions, with hot distilled water.

The precipitates were then shaken into an even suspension and the volume raised up to 500 c.c. each. Nickel in each of the three suspensions was estimated and the volume readjusted till all the suspensions contained the same amount of nickel. The sulphate in each suspension was estimated separately.

The solubility of each one of the suspensions in various concentrations of ammonia solutions was determined as described in the earlier communication (*loc. cit.*). The results

were found to be repeatable within experimental error. Some of the typical results obtained are given below.

TABLE I

Conc. of ammonia soln.	Temperature = 30°. Nickel in suspensions = 98.65 mg. atoms/litre. Samples of hydroxide (Ni dissolved in µg. atom/litre).		
	A.	B.	C.
0.5M	0.1886	0.1636	0.1618
1.0	1.112	1.070	0.8576
1.5	2.098	1.987	1.957
2.0	4.281	3.926	3.816
2.5	6.933	6.679	5.947
3.0	9.061	8.672	7.513
Sulphate associated (mg. ion/litre) _a	0.4028	0.3118	0.2692

It is observed that the precipitate of nickelous hydroxide, obtained by carrying out the precipitation in the hot, differs from the one precipitated in the cold in its colour, which is more whitish green, gelatinous in nature, the ease with which the absorbed sulphate can be removed, and are less soluble in ammonia solutions; while the decrease in solubility due to increase in the quantity of alkali used, decreases in the same order as in the cold.

Effect of Ageing on the Solubility of Nickelous Hydroxide in Ammonia Solutions

The same nickelous hydroxide suspensions (precipitated in the hot and cold by varying amounts of alkali) were stored in glass-stoppered Jena bottles and left to age. Samples of the suspension were drawn out after a lapse of 90 days and 180 days respectively, the nickel content estimated and the volume readjusted. Its solubility in various concentrations of ammonia was then determined. The following tables give the results.

TABLE II

Precipitation in the cold.

Conc. of ammonia soln.	Temperature = 30°. Nickel in suspension = 98.65 mg. atoms/litre. Nickel dissolved in µg. atoms/litre.								
	Age-0.			Age-30 days.			Age-180 days.		
	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.
1.0M	2.561	2.303	2.058	1.217	1.116	0.851	1.119	0.663	0.848
2.0	7.442	6.775	6.357	4.709	4.178	3.651	4.564	3.704	3.136
3.0	14.090	12.540	11.330	10.30	8.559	7.235	10.22	8.551	6.985
Sulphate associated (mg. ions/lit.)	0.5059	0.5012	0.3857	0.4742	0.4470	0.3552	0.4742	0.4174	0.3175

TABLE III

Precipitation in the hot.

Temperature = 30°. Nickel in suspension = 98.65 mg. atoms/litre.

Conc. of ammonia soln.	Nickel dissolved in mg. atoms/litre.								
	Age-0			Age-90 days.			Age-180 days.		
	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.	A.	B.	C.
1.0M	1.112	1.070	0.857	1.093	1.050	0.822	1.009	0.962	0.724
2.0	4.281	3.926	3.813	3.651	3.496	3.409	3.578	3.457	3.067
3.0	9.061	8.672	7.513	8.876	8.390	7.233	8.569	8.098	6.816
Sulphate associated (mg./per litre)	0.4028	0.3188	0.2692	0.3532	0.2885	0.2476	0.3352	0.2658	0.2242

It is thus obvious that the solubility of the nickelous hydroxide precipitated either in the cold or hot with varying amounts of alkali decreases with age.

Effect of Dehydration on the Solubility of Nickelous Hydroxide in Ammonia Solution

Three equal volumes of a sample of nickelous hydroxide suspensions (precipitated in the hot with equivalent alkali) containing 165.4 mg. atoms/litre of nickel and 0.4779 mg. ion/litre of sulphate ions were filtered separately. The first sample was left to dry in air at the room temperature for several days till no further change in weight took place. The second sample was dried at 120° for about 8 to 10 hours till a constant weight was obtained. The third sample was ignited in a crucible to a constant weight, when it turned black due to oxidation of some nickelous oxide.

0.300 G. and 0.500 g. of each one of the dehydrated samples were weighed out in separate glass-stoppered bottles and 75 c.c. of M and 2M ammonia solutions were added to each of the different samples. The bottles were left aside for 18 to 20 hours at the room temperature (30°-31°), the ammoniacal solutions were filtered off and nickel estimated. It was found that the ammoniacal solution from the ignited sample contained no nickel. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Temperature = 30°.

Conc. of ammonia soln.	Amount of nickel dissolved in mg. atoms/litre.		
	Air-dried.	Dried at 120°.	Ignited.
1.0M	1.090	0.7226	Insoluble
2.0	3.953	3.317	Insoluble

The above results show that the solubility of nickelous hydroxide in ammonia decreases as the precipitate becomes more and more dehydrated, till finally it becomes insoluble when ignited.

DISCUSSION

Tables I, II and III show that the purity of the oxide, viz. the amount of sulphate associated, not only decreases with the increasing amount of alkali used for precipitation but also by bringing about the precipitation in the hot.

Tables II, III IV show the remarkable variation in the solubility of the hydroxide, which is found to decrease when it is precipitated either at higher temperatures, aged or dehydrated (cf. Dey and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 181; Mehrotra and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1946, 15A, 161, in the case of cupric oxide). The effect is maximum for the dehydrated samples. Thus, the sample dehydrated in air and at 120°, but still remaining greenish, or dehydrated by igniting, when it turned black, was comparatively inert for the action of ammonia.

This behaviour of nickelous hydroxide can be explained by its amphoteric nature, as has recently been also pointed out by Gayer and Garatt (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1973), who note that the nickelous hydroxide though strongly basic also dissolves in caustic soda.

We are, as has been suggested in part II (*loc. cit.*), of the opinion that the following reactions occur on the surface of the hydroxide itself :

The equations lead to the progressive dehydration of nickelous hydroxide and the scheme, suggested by us, explains the easy solubility of the hydrated oxide in comparison with the solubility of the same substance when it is dehydrated. The decrease in solubility is also likely to be facilitated by excess of alkali (vide equations ii and iii). The results in Table II support this contention, that the decrease in solubility with age of a sample precipitated with deficient alkali in the cold is more than the decrease in solubility with age of a sample precipitated with excess of alkali under similar conditions. Similar conclusion can be arrived at from Table III, where the precipitation is carried out in the hot, with this exception that the change in the solubility with ageing is less remarkable for this sample, when compared to that obtained in the cold. We thus conclude that the precipitation in alkaline medium and heating, ageing or dehydration help equation (ii) to proceed from left to right because of the mutual neutralisation of H⁺ and OH⁻ ions, and formation of the dehydrated oxide, which will have a lesser affinity for electrons, and thus the chances for the formation of ammine will be considerably less.

The amount of sulphate associated will also be less, because the chances of adsorption will be eliminated on the surface of the dehydrated oxide which is now chemically inactive.

We are therefore led to the conclusion that the existence of Ni(OH)⁺ is more capable to initiate the formation of co-ordination compounds with ammonia, because of its positive charge, and thus being helpful for the admission of co-ordinating electrons

of ammonia. Also that the precipitation of the hydroxide by a large excess of alkali, at a higher temperature, ageing and dehydration are all similar processes and are detrimental to the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})^+$ and thus the samples of the hydroxide, subjected to any of the above mentioned conditions, are less soluble in ammonia and consequently unfit for favourable ammine formation.

Further work on the composition of various nickel ammines in solution is in progress.

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